

Self-Driven by Vice

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Abstracts

This paper investigates the complex explanation between vice and self-driven motivation through existentialist and absurdist philosophical frameworks, while integrating insights from humanistic psychology. Drawing on phenomenological analysis, this paper examines how vices—from basic drives to higher-order impulses—function not merely as moral deficits but as authentic expressions of human existence in an absurd world. The study challenges traditional psychological and theological perspectives that view vice primarily as dysfunction, but instead revealing how these ostensibly destructive forces can catalyze personal growth and authentic self-realization and self-motivation. Through historical case studies and philosophical analysis, this paper demonstrates how individuals' struggles with vice often drive societal transformation, illuminating the paradoxical relationship between moral elevation and existential authenticity. The findings suggest that vice, rather than representing mere moral failure, emerges as an inevitable aspect of human beings' search for meaning and authentic self-expression in confronting existence's fundamental absurdity.

I Introduction

The study of human nature often exposes to us paradoxes and contradictions that lie in it. One such concept is that of "vices." Negative features or activities that deviate from the norms of morality are termed vices. However, these vices also act as strong self-motivators for an individual to act against his will and conscience, and also against the norms of society. This paper explores the role of vices as a source of motivation in the contexts of existentialism and absurdism—two schools of philosophy that offer unique insights into the human condition and human behavior. In addition, it creates a conceptual framework aimed at understanding the dialectical relationship existing between vice and self-motivation by synthesizing Existentialist and absurdist philosophical perspectives with a humanistic psychological input. The locus of this essay is, however, placed on the exploration of the relationship between vice and self-motivation through the philosophical lenses of existentialism and absurdism. In *Critique of Pure Reason*, Kant¹ articulates the fundamental boundary of human cognition with regard to epistemology; as such, the deepest questions of vice that have to do with existential meaning and the metaphysical nature of reality end up being beyond the scope of pure reason but rather within the purview of theological inquiry and religious contemplation.

Existentialism emphasizes individualism and the subjective nature of human experience, proposing that life is both absurd and meaningful. Philosophers in this tradition argue that individuals possess the freedom to create their own meaning and values, despite the inherent absurdity of existence. In contrast, absurdism highlights the irrationality of the universe and the lack of inherent meaning in human life, viewing vices as instinctual responses to an absurd world. By examining vices, this paper seeks to deepen our understanding of self-initiated motivation as it relates to the human condition. This research contributes to ongoing discussions in both philosophy and psychology by exploring the complex interplay between human nature and environmental influences. The framework presented here makes three major contributions: (1) integrating existentialist and absurdist views of human motivation with contemporary psychological theories, (2) offering a new interpretation of vice as an authentic expression of existential struggle, and (3) providing practical insights into how individuals navigate the tension between societal norms and authentic self-expression. These findings have significant implications for understanding the paradoxical relationship between human nature, moral constraints, and the role of transgressive behavior in personal development and social evolution.

The paper is structured as follows: Chapter II outlines various forms of vice (such as greed, jealousy, and ambition) and examines their potential to motivate human actions. Chapter III critically analyzes existentialism and absurdism, tracing their historical development and key philosophers to provide a foundation for a deeper exploration of vice in these frameworks. Chapter IV delves into the existentialist view of vice and its implications for the extraction of meaning from human existence. Chapter V explores the interconnections between vice, intrinsic motivation, and absurdism, shedding light on what absurdity reveals about vice and human behavior. Chapter VI presents case studies demonstrating how vice influences self-motivation, drawing from literature, history, and contemporary society. Finally, the discussion and conclusion chapters summarize the findings, compare them with existing theories, and suggest directions for future research. In sum, this report aims to explore the darker aspects of human nature, revealing how vices can act as potent drivers of self-initiated action. It also examines the influence of existentialism and absurdism on these actions, contributing to a deeper understanding of human behavior and the complex contradictions that define our existence.

¹ Immanuel Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, p. A50/B74 (German edition).

II Understanding Vice and Self-Driven Motivation

II.1 Conceptualization and Variants of Vice

Vices are traits or behaviors generally considered morally or socially objectionable by society, and they often have a significant impact on human behavior. These behaviors have been widely examined in both philosophy and psychology, as they can take many forms, such as greed, jealousy, and ambition. Each vice carries different implications and affects behavior in unique ways. Take greed, for example: it stems from a strong desire for wealth, power, or material possessions, often leading individuals to make irrational decisions or act against their own self-interest. On the other hand, jealousy arises from feelings of insecurity or inadequacy, manifesting as hostile behaviors toward others—envying their successes or attempting to undermine their happiness. Ambition is typically seen as a positive motivator until it becomes excessive, driving people to pursue their goals at the expense of others' well-being or by violating moral standards.

At its core, human motivation spans from basic instincts, such as avoiding pain or satisfying hunger, to more complex moral failures. Psychological science reveals that these motivations evolve over time. Basic motivational structures necessary for biological preservation transform through cognitive and social development into what traditional moral philosophy classifies as vice. Humanistic psychology, particularly Maslow's hierarchy of needs, offers a unique lens for understanding this transformation. Unlike traditional psychological paradigms, which often view vices—such as greed, inappropriate ambition, and envy—as simple dysfunctions, humanistic psychology interprets them as distorted expressions of self-actualization. For example, the greedy individual who accumulates more than is necessary does not merely display moral failure but also exemplifies a sophisticated response to existential insecurity. Similarly, excessive ambition is not merely dysfunctional; it is a distorted reflection of the innate drive toward self-realization. This transformation raises challenges for rational analysis. While Kant's *Critique of Pure Reason* attempts to constrain human behavior within rational frameworks, vices emerge from a pre-rational foundation, remaining outside the scope of pure reason. These motivational systems arise from what theological and religious traditions have long referred to as the "fallen" aspect of human consciousness. Historically, religion and theology have understood vice not only as behavioral aberrations but as intrinsic to the human condition. While this perspective has been marginalized in contemporary psychological debates, it aligns with increasing understandings in psychology regarding how basic drives evolve into complex moral behaviors. The irrational nature of vice poses significant challenges for existing psychological models. In today's world of cognitive methodologies, which emphasize rational cognitive processes and behavioral change, the existential dimensions of vice are often overlooked. These impulses do not stem from flawed cognition but from fundamental attitudes toward existence itself.

These primary motivational structures, necessary for biological preservation, are transformed through cognitive and social development into what traditional moral philosophy classifies as vice. The key to this transformation lies in humanistic psychology, especially Maslow's hierarchical model. In contrast, traditional psychological paradigms often view the vices—such as greed, inappropriate ambition, and bitter comparisons—as simple dysfunctions or deficiencies. On the other hand, humanistic psychology sees them as subtler but twisted expressions of self-actualization. The greedy person who gathers more than any reasonable necessity is seen to exemplify not only moral failing but a sophisticated response to the existential insecurity. Likewise, excessive ambition is not taken as pure dysfunction; rather, it is a warped echo of innate self-realization drive. Now, the ways in which basic impulses develop into more elaborate vices pose some unique challenges to

rational analysis. Though the Kantian pure reason tries with all its might to constrain human behavior within the limits of rational frameworks, these pre-rational foundations of vice always remain un-categorical. These motivational systems operate on a register prior to rational thought, emerging from what theological and religious traditions have long described as the fallen aspect of human consciousness. Classically, religion and theology have placed vice into large metaphysical frameworks, understanding it as not just a behavioral aberration but rather as something to do with the very humanness of humanity. Much marginalized in contemporary psychological debates, this perspective finds kinship with an increasing understanding of how basic drives are elaborated into complex moral behaviors. The religious understanding of vice as inherent, not just purely acquired, finds a kindred spirit in psychological discoveries of innate motivational systems. The irrational nature of vice does pose considerable difficulties for existing psychological models. In today's world of cognitive methodologies that foreground rational cognitive processes and behavioral change, the existential elements of vice are often poorly understood. Such impulses run counter to cognitive reformation precisely because they arise from the pre-rational strata of consciousness and represent not mistaken cognition but fundamental attitudes toward existence itself. The roots of vice are complex and influenced by a host of factors. Scholars say that norms of society, experiences of life, and even genetic predispositions may influence such behaviors. So, for instance, societies wholly focused on material possessions and competition will give birth to greed and ambition with ease, while those cultures or societies that base their worthiness on comparison and ranking tend to enslave with envy. Likewise, some personality traits, such as neuroticism or the tendency toward dominance, may predispose certain people to develop these less-than-desirable characteristics.

II.2 Vice as an Intrinsic Motivator

Psychologically, vices emerge primarily from desires and emotions that can overwhelm rational thought. Academic literature reveals that intense emotions—such as anger or fear—can precipitate aggressive or destructive behaviors. Conversely, the pursuit of pleasure or the impulse to avoid pain may drive individuals toward risk-taking, manifested through addiction or reckless conduct. Traditional psychological paradigms tend to conceptualize vices as pathological deficiencies requiring therapeutic intervention, while theological perspectives frame them as moral transgressions. This paper, however, offers a more nuanced theoretical exploration by examining vices not merely as ethical failures, but as complex psychological mechanisms of self-actualization within an inherently absurd existential framework. Vices should be understood as sophisticated defense strategies originating from unresolved existential conflicts. When individuals encounter insurmountable challenges in satisfying higher-order psychological needs, they often retreat to more primitive motivational structures. From this perspective, vices represent distorted expressions of fundamental unmet needs. Take greed, for instance: it frequently emerges as a compensatory mechanism for feelings of inadequacy or insecurity—a psychological response to the profound fear of insufficiency in an uncertain world. Drawing on Maslow's hierarchy of needs, individuals who struggle to achieve self-esteem or a sense of belonging may attempt to validate their existential worth through the accumulation of material possessions or social prestige. Similarly, envy—perhaps the most corrosive of vices—functions as an emotional shield against feelings of inferiority and disconnection. When individuals perceive others as possessing something they lack—whether success, wealth, or status—they respond with envy. This vice becomes a desperate attempt to validate one's existence through comparative assessment. These psychological phenomena are not mere moral failings but complex existential responses: the ongoing struggle to synchronize one's self-perception with external reality. Rather than confronting these profound emotional experiences, individuals engage in behaviors that provide temporary relief while ultimately deepening their alienation from authentic self-understanding. By integrating Heidegger's concept of "thrownness" (*Geworfenheit*) and Camus's philosophy of the absurd, this analysis reframes vices as existential responses to the human condition—marked by

ontological anxiety and fundamental estrangement. Through an exploration of both primary motivational structures and higher-order vices, the paper demonstrates how seemingly self-destructive impulses can paradoxically become vehicles for genuine self-realization. This perspective challenges both Kantian rational ethics and the optimistic ontology of humanistic psychology, revealing a fundamental tension between moral enhancement and existential authenticity. The pursuit of a meaningful life, this analysis suggests, necessarily involves engaging with what traditional morality labels as "vice"—not as a moral failure, but as an understandable consequence of confronting life's inherent meaninglessness. For instance, greed often compensates for feelings of inadequacy or insecurity, serving as a response to the fear of inadequacy in an uncertain world. According to Maslow's hierarchy of needs, those who fail to achieve self-esteem or belonging may attempt to fulfill these needs by accumulating material possessions or social prestige, believing these external symbols will affirm their worth. Similarly, envy is a corrosive vice that emerges from feelings of inferiority and disconnection. When individuals perceive others as having something they lack—whether it be success, wealth, or status—they react with envy. This vice serves as a defense against existential inadequacy, reflecting the individual's attempt to validate their existence by comparing themselves to others. These vices are not simply moral failings but psychological responses to existential dilemmas: the struggle to align one's self-concept with the reality of the external world. Rather than confronting these core emotional experiences, individuals engage in behaviors that provide temporary relief but ultimately lead to deeper alienation from their true selves.

In an absurd society, vice exceeds its conventional moral conception, preparing and stepping towards the existential attitude—the expression of the Dionysian will to power that rebels against normative constraints and justifies individual existence. In conditions defined by mediocrity and systematic degeneration, vice is transformed into a revolutionary form of self-realization in which transgression is not a failure but a basic gesture of revolt against the absurd. A Nietzschean genealogy reconceptualizes vice, not as a moral lack, but as something productive of existential creativity. It reinterprets the harmful aspects of vice as a pathway toward self-overcoming in response to the internal chaos in life, which finds an enhancement of the individual's ability to throw meaning into a meaninglessness existence. In this sense, vice is figured as a threshold space through which the individual reaches out to and touches their circumscribed existence, using transgression as a strategy for both self-preservation and empowerment. Rather than an immoral act, vice here initiates a process of self-transformation in and through which the contradictions of society are distilled into a potent mode of resistance. In the Nietzschean discourse, this concept is realized as the will to power—an active declaration of life force amidst a universe that is indifferent. Vice is presented as a way of existential autonomy that breaks down the simple opposition between good and evil, reconceptualizing virtue in relation to personal strength and genuineness. Within this nonsensical realm, vice participates in the process of self-actualization. The claim to individual liberty finds its fulfillment in embracing vice—whether expressed in ambition, greed, or other forms of excess—creating meaning in a world that has none. The concept here relevant to Nietzsche is that of the *Übermensch*: vice is not a moral weakness but a critical expression of human life force and self-determination in a world that offers no readymade meaning. Thus, vice in this context is not a moral failure but a profound existential tool. It allows the individual to navigate the absurd, to affirm his or her powers, and to convert them into the alchemical process of self-creation. In a society that imposes meaninglessness, vice would then become the radical form of liberation from it and of self-empowerment—a very real manifestation of Nietzsche's philosophy of life affirmation.

III Existentialism and Absurdism

Existentialism is philosophically committed to reshaping our understanding of human nature, particularly the relationship between personal motivation and life's absurdity. Absurdism, most notably represented by Albert Camus, highlights the conflict between the search for meaning in life and the indifference of the universe. Both philosophies emphasize individual experience and personal choice, confronting us with the unsettling possibility that life may lack intrinsic meaning. Such existential thinking compels individuals to carve out their own personal meaning, even in an unpredictable and absurd world.

III.1 Existentialism

Existentialism is a philosophical movement that centers on the individual's experience and existence. It raises fundamental questions about the meaning of life, the nature of humanity, and the freedom and responsibility each person bears. The term "existentialism," coined by Jean-Paul Sartre in his 1946 lecture "Existentialism is a Humanism," brought together ideas that had developed in the 19th and early 20th centuries. At its core, existentialism affirms individualism—the belief that individuals are self-reliant and responsible for their own lives. As Sartre famously states, "Man is nothing else but the sum of his actions," emphasizing that we are defined by our choices and actions. Existentialists argue for the freedom to develop one's life and meaning, but this freedom is inseparable from responsibility. Furthermore, existentialism addresses the human condition, particularly the experience of living without clear purpose or meaning, or in a world that can often feel absurd.

III.2 Absurdism

Absurdism, as a philosophy, is even more radical than existentialism in its treatment of human experience. It posits that the universe is inherently irrational, and life itself is absurd. The term "absurd" was popularized by playwright Samuel Beckett in his 1953 play *Waiting for Godot*. Absurdism builds on existentialist themes but takes a more radical stance, asserting that life is devoid of meaning and that humanity's desire to find purpose clashes with the universe's indifference. Camus captures this tension with his concept of "the absurd," which refers to the conflict between our yearning for significance and the chaotic, meaningless nature of existence. Camus famously encapsulates this idea: "The absurd is born out of this confrontation between the human call and the unreasonable silence of the world." This highlights the central conflict of absurdism—our human desires for meaning in a universe that offers none. According to Camus, trying to find purpose in life often feels futile because there is no rational structure to reality. He reflects this sentiment in the phrase, "The more I love the world, the more I know it's made up of people," capturing the tension between our hopes and the chaotic nature of existence. Absurdism also explores the emotional experience of absurdity—the feeling of meaninglessness that arises when one realizes life has no inherent purpose. Camus believes that the absurdity of life can only be confronted through rebellion or refusal. His famous declaration, "I rebel; therefore, we exist," underscores the importance of rejecting passive acceptance of life's meaninglessness. For Camus, suicide is the coward's escape from the absurd. Life must be lived fully, with meaning found through personal rebellion and action. This idea is embodied in the character of Meursault in Camus's *The Stranger*, who confronts the absurdity of life and chooses to live authentically, giving his life meaning through his actions and decisions.

While existentialism emphasizes the creation of meaning through individual choice, absurdism, as developed by Camus, acknowledges the futility of such a search and advocates instead for active rebellion in the face of the absurd. The shift from existentialism to absurdism represents a significant leap in thought about human existence, enriching our understanding of life's complexities. Both philosophies offer valuable insights into human motivation, particularly in relation to vice and ethical behavior.

IV Vice, Motivation, and Existentialism

Existentialism is a philosophical movement that highlights the absurdity and importance of human existence, offering a fresh view on the concept of vice and its impact on behavior. This chapter explores how existentialist thinkers like Heidegger and Sartre have interpreted vice, examining how it can act as a source of self-driven motivation and contribute to the search for meaning in life.

IV.1 Vice and the Meaning of Existence

In the existentialist framework, vices—defined as negative traits or morally questionable behaviors—can serve as manifestations of an individual's struggle to assert their freedom and identity. Sartre's concept of "bad faith" illustrates this dynamic, where individuals may adopt vices as a means of evading authentic existence. By conforming to societal expectations or succumbing to self-deception, they obscure their true selves, thus engaging in behaviors that may be deemed as vices. Existentialism offers a profound framework for understanding the role of vice in shaping human behavior and existence, particularly through the insights of key philosophers like Heidegger and Sartre. Each presents a distinct perspective on how vice intersects with the complexities of the human condition.

IV.2 Vice and the Existence

Heidegger, in "Being and Time," emphasizes authenticity, suggesting that feelings of alienation and a sense of being "homeless" can drive individuals to adopt vices such as consumerism and narcissism. He views these behaviors as a retreat from authenticity, a response to the "angst" or fear of confronting one's responsibilities and choices. For Heidegger, engaging in vice represents a departure from true selfhood and highlights the struggle to live authentically in a seemingly indifferent world. Sartre, conversely, adopts a more proactive stance, positing that vice can be an expression of individual freedom. In "Existentialism and Human Emotions," he argues that in a universe devoid of inherent meaning, individuals create their own significance through their choices, including the choice to engage in vice. For Sartre, these actions are not flaws but conscious responses to life's absurdity, asserting control over a chaotic existence.

In existential phenomenology, Martin Heidegger's rethinking of human existence shifts the focus from eternal essences to the fundamental reality of our finitude. Unlike Platonic thought, which seeks transcendence through immutable forms, Heidegger's insight centers on Dasein—our being-in-the-world—as inherently finite. Temporality, for Heidegger, is not an external constraint on existence, but its very essence. Far from being a limitation, finitude is the condition for authentic being. In this context, vice is reimagined not as a moral failure but as an expression of our existential limitations. Rather than an aberration, vice reflects the tension between our finite nature and the awareness of our temporal horizon. It becomes a way of engaging with the uncertainties of life, a means of confronting the existential anxiety that arises from our finite existence. Heidegger critiques the Platonic notion of eternal essence, replacing it with a view of human existence defined by three key features: radical temporality, ontological incompleteness, and finite possibilities. Our being is not static but an unfolding process. We do not have a predetermined essence; our potential is both generative and limited by time. Within this framework, vice is not simply moral transgression but an ontological response to our finitude. It's a negotiation between the recognition of our limitations and the desire to transcend them. In this sense, vice becomes a way of asserting our freedom within the constraints of existence—an existential tool for self-creation. It is through this struggle that we define meaning in a world that resists easy answers. Vice, as a phenomenological mechanism, allows individuals to confront their incompleteness and resist societal or moral expectations. It is a form of self-definition, where the act of transgression becomes a path to asserting one's own existence in a world of inevitable dissolution. Repositioning vice within the structure of temporality challenges traditional moral views, inviting us to see transgression not as a failure but as an essential part of existential exploration. Heidegger's insight reframes vice as an intrinsic aspect of human being, a manifestation of the tension between our finite nature and the need to create meaning in a world that

does not offer it easily. Heidegger's philosophy offers a radical reinterpretation of vice: not as moral failing, but as an authentic expression of our temporal, finite existence. In this view, vice becomes a way to engage with life's uncertainties—a dialogue with our own existence. This understanding invites a deeper, more nuanced perspective on human behavior, recognizing that our transgressions are not mere moral lapses but profound expressions of our struggle with the human condition.

Heidegger, Sartre, and the Reinterpretation of Vice as Existential Freedom

In *Being and Time*, Martin Heidegger's exploration of "authenticity" brings a radical reinterpretation of vice, suggesting that feelings of alienation and "homelessness" in a disenchanting world often lead individuals to adopt vices like consumerism and narcissism. Yet, these behaviors are not simply moral failures but expressions of a deeper existential anxiety—a retreat from authentic being. Heidegger's concept of angst, the dread of confronting one's freedom and ultimate responsibility, frames vice as an evasion of the call to be authentically oneself. In this sense, vices are not merely indulgences or excesses but represent an attempt to shield oneself from the weight of existence itself. The tension between *Dasein* (being-there) and authenticity suggests that vice, as Heidegger would see it, can be viewed as an existential coping mechanism, a resistance against the self-discovery that true freedom demands. In Heidegger's view, engaging in vice reveals an individual's avoidance of confronting their finitude—the inescapable nature of our temporal existence. Sartre, however, offers a more proactive reading of vice, one that sees it as an expression of existential freedom. For Sartre, vice is a conscious and deliberate act that reflects an individual's autonomy in a meaningless universe. In *Existentialism and Human Emotions*, Sartre argues that in the face of the absurd, we are not bound by moral laws but are free to choose our actions, including engaging in vices. These actions, according to Sartre, are not failures but responses to the absence of meaning. Sartre's focus on choice and personal responsibility shifts the locus of meaning from external moral norms to internal, self-created values. In this context, vices are not moral shortcomings but an assertion of freedom, a defiance of the preordained paths laid out by society.

Existential Phenomenology: The Path of Vice as Ontological Self-Creation

Heidegger's existential phenomenology shifts the focus of human existence from eternal essences to the temporal realities of finitude and contingency. Contrary to Platonic ideas of transcendence through eternal Forms, Heidegger's focus on *Dasein*—our being-in-the-world—emphasizes the radical temporality of existence. Temporality is not an external constraint on existence but its essence; it is through time that the human being comes to understand itself. In this framework, vice is reframed not as a moral transgression but as an existential tool for self-creation in the face of our limitations. Vice, then, is not an aberration of the moral order but a confrontation with finitude. It embodies the tension between our existential need to transcend our limitations and the reality that we are bound by time. Instead of viewing vice as a "fall from grace" or a moral failure, we might view it as an attempt to assert meaning in a world that resists it. It becomes an active engagement with the absurdity of life and a form of resistance against a universe that offers no inherent meaning. Heidegger's view of vice as a negotiation with time and finitude reframes it as a form of freedom—a space where we can assert ourselves in a world that offers no preordained answers. In this sense, vice is not merely about moral transgression but about self-assertion. It is the negotiation between the recognition of our limitations and the desire to transcend them. As an act of rebellion against the constraints of existence, vice can be viewed as a form of self-definition, a radical refusal to accept societal or moral norms that define the "correct" way of being. In embracing vice, individuals may assert their own existence in a world that constantly pushes them toward dissolution and decay.

Vice as a Dialogue with Death and Transience

Expanding further, we can consider how vice operates not merely as a reaction to life's meaninglessness but also as a way to engage with the reality of death—our ultimate finitude. In confronting mortality, vice becomes a form of self-creation that engages not only with the limitations of existence but with its inevitable end. In

the face of death, vices such as hedonism or excess might be seen as a response to the brevity of life, an attempt to extract meaning or satisfaction from an existence that is destined for oblivion. The embrace of vice, then, might not be nihilistic surrender, but a profound dialogue with death itself—a way of saying: "If I must die, let me die in defiance of the world's indifference." In this light, vices take on a radically different meaning—they become expressions of our resistance to the existential void. They are not simply moral failings or signs of existential despair but a confrontation with our temporality. In this sense, vice offers an opportunity for self-affirmation within the constraints of time—a way of marking one's existence in a world that ultimately refuses to grant it inherent meaning. Vice is not only the rebellion against social norms or moral expectations but the rebellion against the inevitability of *nothingness*. By engaging with vice, individuals enact a defiant assertion of their agency in the face of their own mortality.

Repositioning Vice: An Essential Element of Existential Exploration

Thus, vice becomes an essential part of existential exploration—a mechanism through which individuals negotiate their relationship with their own finitude and the absurdity of existence. It is through these acts of transgression that one attempts to carve out a space for personal freedom and self-assertion. Heidegger's radical reinterpretation of vice calls us to reconsider moral transgression not as a failure, but as an essential aspect of the human condition—a necessary form of self-exploration in a world that resists easy answers. In this way, vice is not a moral lapse, but a profound expression of our struggle with the limitations of time, mortality, and meaninglessness. By repositioning vice within the context of temporality and finitude, we are invited to see it not as a deviation from moral norms but as a necessary part of our ongoing dialogue with existence. In this existential framework, vice becomes a tool for self-creation, a way to confront our own limitations, and a means to engage with the absurdity of life. This view offers a deeper, more nuanced perspective on human behavior, allowing us to see our transgressions not as moral failings but as authentic expressions of our struggle to find meaning and define ourselves in an indifferent world.

IV.2.1 The Existential Void and the Genesis of Vices

The concept of *Geworfenheit*²—the idea of being "thrown" into existence, the original quote: "Dasein ist zunächst und zumeist verfallen."—forms the cornerstone of understanding human motivation. As articulated by Martin Heidegger, we find ourselves thrust into a world we did not choose, shaped by forces beyond our control, in a universe that is often indifferent to our existence. This thrownness reveals the existential void that is a fundamental feature of the human condition. In this void, we encounter not only the anxiety of being, but also the impulse to find meaning and order in an inherently disordered world. At the heart of human motivation lies a profound tension: the struggle to fill this void. In the absence of predetermined meaning, we are left to forge our own path, often by responding to the world with the tools we have at hand. Initially, this might take the form of basic physiological drives—pain avoidance, hunger, and survival. However, as these elemental needs are met, the human being is faced with a deeper, more complex need for significance, belonging, and self-actualization. This shift from basic survival to existential fulfillment forms the fertile ground for the development of vices. Vices are not merely moral failings; they are existential responses to the abyss of meaninglessness that *Geworfenheit* exposes. As we face the irreducible fact of being cast into a world that offers no intrinsic meaning, we often resort to these vices to create artificial constructs of value and control, attempting to compensate for the deeper existential discomfort we cannot easily name. In this way, vices become a form of self-driven existential compensation. They are attempts to fill the internal void, to create meaning in an inherently meaningless world. As individuals, we may strive for wealth, power, or social status

²*Being and Time*, Heidegger, *Being and Time*, §4.2.1, pp. 184–188 (German edition)

not merely for the pleasures these things afford, but as a means of constructing an identity in response to the thrownness of our existence. In this way, vice can be understood as both an unconscious response to the void and a self-perpetuating cycle, driven by the same existential disorientation that Heidegger describes.

IV.2.2 Vices as Distorted Motivations: The Path to Inauthenticity

Transcending inauthentic existence through self-reflection, rather than direct negation, vice versa, advancing towards an authentic state of being. The existential nature of *Geworfenheit*—our being "thrown" into a world without clear purpose—renders it an inherently ambiguous and unsettling condition. Heidegger's concept of being-in-the-world underscores the difficulty of reconciling the freedom we experience with the constraints imposed by the world around us. Human beings are confronted with the tension between authentic self-expression and the external demands of society, culture, and history³. This tension can lead to a distortion of motivation, where the drive for material success, status, and recognition overshadows more meaningful pursuits. In humanistic psychology, this distortion is conceptualized as a shift from authentic existence to inauthentic existence. Vices such as greed, ambition, and envy are not just individual moral failures, but signs of inauthenticity. In their essence, these vices reflect a failure to confront the truth of one's existence. Instead of embracing the existential void as a space for authentic self-creation, individuals attempt to fill it with external markers of success and social approval. The individual who chases after material wealth or social status is, in essence, using these external goals as a shield against confronting the deeper, more uncomfortable realities of existence. In a sense, vice becomes the escape from authenticity. Rather than embracing the uncertainty of existence and the responsibility that comes with it, individuals pursue goals that are externally validated, seeking external markers of success that ultimately prove hollow. This process leads to further alienation from the self, as the individual becomes more deeply embedded in an external narrative of success, rather than their own inner truth. In this way, vices are not merely destructive patterns of behavior; they are mechanisms of avoidance—avoidance of the inherent freedom, responsibility, and anxiety that come with confronting one's true existential condition. As human beings, we are "thrown" into a world that offers no predetermined meaning, and our existential struggle is to create meaning where none exists. Yet when we seek to substitute external validation for internal authenticity, we become trapped in a cycle of existential alienation.

IV.2.3 The Cycle of Self-Destruction: Vice as a Regressive Force

The most insidious aspect of vice is that it is self-perpetuating. The more we engage in vice as a means of coping with the existential void, the more we entrench ourselves in a cycle of self-destruction. Greed, for example, might offer momentary relief from anxiety and a sense of power over the chaotic world. However, over time, the satisfaction derived from wealth and status fades, leading to an even greater need for more power, more wealth, and more recognition. This cycle is self-reinforcing: the more we chase after external goals, the further we move from the authentic self, and the deeper the existential void grows. This regressive cycle of vice is a fundamental feature of the existential condition. It is a response to the realization that, despite our best efforts, the world does not offer the permanent, stable meaning we so desperately seek. In chasing after external validation, we increasingly experience the emptiness that defines human existence, reinforcing the very impulses that drive us toward vice in the first place. Thus, vices are both a cause and a consequence of existential alienation. They are the symptoms of a deeper crisis—the inability to reconcile the demands of the external world with the internal yearning for authenticity and self-actualization. This crisis is rooted in the very nature of our existence: we are thrown into a world that is both unfamiliar and uncontrollable, and our

³ *Being and Time*, Heidegger, *Being and Time*, §4.2.2, pp. 254–262 (German edition). Key concept: "Human beings face a tension between self-expression and the demands of the external society." Corresponding section in *Being and Time*: Second part, §4, "Falling" (*Verfallen*).

response to this dissonance is often to seek refuge in destructive patterns of behavior.

IV.2.4 Moving Beyond Vice: A Path to Authenticity

The solution to this existential crisis lies not in the rejection of our desires or motivations, but in transforming them. By confronting the truth of our *Geworfenheit*, we can begin to move beyond the self-destructive cycles of vice. Humanistic psychology provides a roadmap for this transformation. Rather than seeking external validation or fleeing from the existential void, we can learn to embrace it as a space for authentic self-creation. The path to authenticity requires acknowledging the inherent tension between our freedom and our limitations, between our aspirations and our realities. It is only through accepting our thrownness—the fact that we are not the architects of our circumstances but are nevertheless free to create meaning within them—that we can transcend the self-perpetuating nature of vice. Through self-awareness, self-acceptance, and the pursuit of self-actualization, we can begin to reorient our motivations away from the destructive impulses of vice and toward more meaningful, self-directed goals. This process involves a radical shift in perspective, one that allows us to confront the existential void not as a source of anxiety, but as an opportunity for authentic growth and creative expression.

In conclusion, the existentialist exploration of vice reveals its complex role in the human experience. Heidegger, Sartre⁴⁵ each contribute unique insights, underscoring that while vice may reflect a reaction to existential challenges, it also presents opportunities for personal growth and the creation of meaning in an otherwise chaotic world. The connection between vice and existence doesn't have an indispensable relationship, but more as a prerequisite since the existentialist perspective encourages a deeper understanding of vice as an integral part of the human journey. By acknowledging the role of vices in shaping individual motivations and actions, existentialism invites individuals to engage with their inner conflicts and make conscious choices that reflect their authentic selves, thus redefining the notion of vice within the broader context of personal freedom and responsibility. Ignoring the fact that with different level of education, people have vice ---- no matter one has a relatively prestige or one lacks education but who is also kind instead of being rude, vice accompanies by human nature, which made it inerascable and rational. And the negative traits, as the emphasis on individual freedom by committing crimes, or the action to find the meaning of existence to overcome the insignificance is a motivation putting human to go forward.

V Vice, Motivation, and Absurdism

V.1 Vice and the Meaning of Absurdism

In this framework, particularly as articulated through Camus's notion of the absurd and its relationship to human existence, provides a distinct perspective on the nature of vice. While existentialism emphasizes authenticity and freedom, absurdism illuminates how vices emerge as rational responses to an fundamentally irrational universe—manifestations of the tension between human beings' desperate search for meaning and the world's profound indifference to this quest. Vice isn't simply seen as a moral failing; rather, it emerges as a natural response to the absurdity of existence. It can reflect the human drive to seek meaning, even when faced with meaninglessness. Camus illustrates this in his essay "The Myth of Sisyphus," where he portrays Sisyphus as a figure who, despite his endless and futile struggle against the gods, finds a sense of purpose in his defiance. This idea of vice as a reaction to the absurd can also be found in other absurdist works. Characters in the plays of Eugene Ionesco, for example, often behave in bizarre and irrational ways, driven by emotions like jealousy, ambition, or a need for attention. This highlights the notion that, in a world devoid of inherent meaning, individuals may resort to vice as a way to forge their own sense of purpose and significance.

⁴ *Being and Nothingness*, Sartre, *Being and Nothingness*, Part 3, "Being-for-Others", pp. 300–350 (German edition).

⁵ *Existentialism is a Humanism*, Sartre, *Existentialism is a Humanism* (1946), pp. 22–23 (French edition), "Man is nothing else but what he makes of himself."

V.2 Vice and the Absurd

Absurdism, particularly as articulated by Albert Camus, presents a unique lens through which to examine the role of vice in human behavior. Central to absurdism is the notion that life is inherently devoid of meaning, leading to a profound sense of conflict between human desires and the irrationality of the universe. This framework suggests that individuals may turn to vices as a response to the absurdity they encounter in their lives. The connection between vice and absurdity is further examined through absurdism, which highlights the irrational nature of the universe and the absurdity of human existence. In *The Myth of Sisyphus*, Camus presents the absurd as the fundamental contradiction between human beings' relentless desire for meaning and purpose, and the universe's complete silence in response to these metaphysical yearnings. Through this theoretical lens, vices can be understood not as moral failures or psychological deficits, but as conscious or unconscious strategies for confronting the absurd condition. The individual who succumbs to greed, for instance, is not merely seeking material satisfaction, but attempting to construct artificial meaning through accumulation—a response to the universe's fundamental meaninglessness. However, Camus also champions the power of choice, suggesting that individuals can resist these temptations and instead find meaning through self-acceptance and confronting life's inherent absurdity.

In absurdism, vice becomes a way for characters to cope with this sense of absurdity. Driven by a desire to find meaning, they often turn to vice as a means of asserting control and creating purpose in their lives. For example, in Camus's *"The Stranger,"* Meursault's seemingly indifferent or nihilistic behavior can be interpreted as a form of vice that arises from his struggle to find meaning in an absurd world. This view challenges conventional moral standards, suggesting that vice isn't merely a deviation from morality but a reaction to the absurdity of existence. From the absurdist perspective, vice and self-driven motivation are closely linked. It may become a motivating force, pushing individuals to act against societal norms in their quest for purpose. A clear example is Cléante in Molière's *"The Imaginary Invalid,"* whose ambition and envy lead him to manipulate those around him for personal gain. This illustrates the idea that, in a world lacking inherent meaning, people often create their own meanings through vice. Since they posit that the recognition of life's absurdity can lead to a liberating acceptance of one's own limitations and desires. In this light, vices are not merely moral shortcomings but can also be viewed as expressions of an individual's struggle to create meaning in a meaningless world. By embracing their vices, individuals may navigate the absurdity of life in a manner that reflects their authenticity and agency.

The absurdity of existence can create a void that individuals try to fill with various forms of vice, which allow them to express their desires, ambitions, and fears in an irrational world. This perspective redefines traditional views of morality, suggesting that vice isn't just a sign of a flawed character but a response to life's inherent absurdity. In conclusion, exploring the relationship between vice, self-driven motivation, and absurdism offers a unique lens on human behavior. In a universe perceived as absurd, individuals are often propelled to seek meaning through vice, which serves as both motivation and a way to assert control. This relationship between vice and absurdism illuminates the complexities of human motivation in the face of an indifferent universe since it also encourages a nuanced understanding of how vices can function as both a coping mechanism and a source of personal meaning, enabling individuals to assert their identities and navigate the challenges of existence with a sense of agency and resilience, the absurdist framework suggests that vice may serve as a form of rebellion against the meaninglessness of existence. Just as Camus's Sisyphus finds meaning in the very futility of his task, the individual engaging in vice might be seen as engaging in a form of metaphysical defiance—choosing to act meaningfully in full awareness of the ultimate meaninglessness of all action. This perspective transforms our understanding of vice from a moral or psychological problem to an existential strategy—albeit one that ultimately fails to resolve the fundamental absurdity of the human condition.

The Role of Vice in Defiance of the Absurd: A Creative Response to Life's Meaninglessness

Absurdism, as articulated by Albert Camus, provides a profound lens for understanding the role of vice in human behavior. In this framework, life's inherent lack of meaning creates a fundamental tension between human desires and the irrational universe. As Camus argues, the absurd is born from the confrontation between humanity's yearning for significance and the universe's complete silence in response. However, this confrontation does not necessarily lead to despair. Instead, vice can be reinterpreted as a creative response to the absurd condition—an attempt to carve out meaning in a universe that refuses to offer it. This new understanding suggests that vice is not a moral failure, but rather a form of self-assertion, a deliberate choice to create meaning, however artificial, in a world devoid of inherent purpose. Camus's concept of rebellion provides a useful framework for understanding how vice can function as a form of resistance. Much like the mythical figure of Sisyphus, who finds meaning in the futility of his task, the individual who engages in vice might be seen as performing an act of metaphysical defiance—a conscious assertion of self in the face of a meaningless universe. In this sense, vice is a tool of self-creation, a statement of freedom in a world that offers no preordained path. Far from being an escape from life's absurdity, vice becomes a form of engagement with it—a means to resist its suffocating indifference by creating one's own meaning, even if that meaning is fleeting or ultimately illusory.

Vice as Existential Rebellion: A Dialogical Response to the Absurd

In this view, vice is not merely an expression of moral lapse but a dialogue with the absurd itself. By engaging in vice, individuals are not submitting to a pathological compulsion but are making an existential statement about their refusal to accept a world devoid of meaning. Vice becomes a way of asserting one's individuality and agency in a universe that denies both. The very act of vice can be seen as an affirmation of existence, a protest against the void that threatens to consume the individual. In this sense, vice becomes an act of resilience, a strategy for asserting one's existence in a world that resists easy answers. This interpretation redefines vice as a philosophical strategy rather than a moral or psychological flaw. It is a form of rebellion, not just against societal norms, but against the fundamental absurdity of existence itself. In the face of life's inherent meaninglessness, individuals turn to vice not as a form of surrender but as a metaphysical tool for creating their own significance. Through the engagement with vice, they enact a form of freedom that transcends the mundane constraints of conventional morality. The more we embrace the absurd, the more we reclaim our agency, and the more we recognize that our choices, however misguided, are what allow us to assert meaning in an indifferent world.

The Ultimate Failure of Vice: Navigating the Boundaries of Human Existence

It is crucial to recognize, however, that the ultimate failure of vice is not merely a tragic or destructive aspect of human nature. In the context of absurdism, vice can be seen as a necessary failure, a part of our ongoing struggle to make sense of an inherently meaningless existence. It is through this failure that we encounter the true nature of our existence, one that is finite, limited, and temporal. In the end, vice may not provide the answers to life's absurd questions, but it offers a profound affirmation of our struggle—a reminder that even in the face of futility, we are actively engaged in the process of becoming. In this way, vice represents the inevitable human confrontation with time and death, an existential reckoning with the limits of human existence. The recognition of this failure should not lead to despair but to a deeper acceptance of the human condition—an acknowledgment that our actions, our vices, and our transgressions are part of the larger existential project of self-definition. This perspective allows us to see vice not as a path to self-destruction but as a means of existential navigation, a tool that enables us to cope with the inevitability of meaninglessness while still asserting our agency in the world.

VI Case Studies

The relationship between human agency and vice presents a compelling paradox in existentialist thought: individuals, while ostensibly free to choose their actions, often find themselves driven by vices that seem to operate with an almost autonomous force. The primary objective is to demonstrate how vice can serve as a powerful motivator, often pushing individuals to act against their moral beliefs or societal norms. This analysis examines how self-driven motivations, particularly when rooted in vice, create a complex interplay between human freedom and self-imposed constraints, ultimately leading to patterns of self-destruction that transcend historical and cultural boundaries.

VI.1 The Dialectic of Freedom and Vice

The existentialist perspective reveals a fundamental tension in human nature: our capacity for rational choice coexists with an inexorable pull toward self-destructive behaviors. This contradiction manifests most powerfully in cases where individuals, despite their awareness of potential consequences, become agents of their own downfall through vice-driven actions. Consider the case of Nikolai Tesla, whose brilliant innovations were ultimately undermined by his obsessive perfectionism and inability to compromise—a vice that, while driving his genius, also ensured his isolation and eventual destitution. This example illustrates how vice can simultaneously serve as both motivation and destruction, creating what Sartre might term an "authentic inauthenticity"—a genuine expression of freedom that paradoxically leads to self-imprisonment.

VI.2 The Collective Manifestation of Individual Vices

When examining historical catastrophes, we often find that collective disasters are rooted in the aggregation of individual vice-driven decisions. The 2008 financial crisis serves as a compelling example: individual traders and executives, driven by greed and hubris, created a systemic risk that ultimately led to global economic collapse. This case demonstrates how personal vices, when operating within institutional frameworks, can create what Hannah Arendt⁶ termed the "banality of evil"—where ordinary individuals, acting from mundane motivations, contribute to extraordinary catastrophes.

VI.3 The Technological Amplification of Vice

In contemporary society, technology serves as an amplifier of vice-driven behavior, creating what might be termed a "digital acceleration of the absurd." The case of social media addiction among technology executives—who, despite understanding the psychological mechanisms their platforms exploit, find themselves unable to moderate their own usage—presents a modern iteration of the vice paradox. These individuals, while intellectually aware of their behavior's destructive nature, remain caught in cycles of compulsive engagement, highlighting what Kierkegaard might recognize as the "sickness unto death" in its modern form.

VI.4 The Existential Weight of Repetition

Perhaps most profound is the pattern of repetition observed in vice-driven behavior. Despite historical precedents and clear evidence of destructive outcomes, individuals and societies continue to enact similar patterns of vice-driven decision-making. The recurring nature of financial bubbles, from the Dutch tulip mania to contemporary cryptocurrency speculation, demonstrates what Nietzsche⁷ termed "eternal recurrence" in the context of human vice. This repetition suggests a deeper existential truth: that vice serves not merely as a moral failing but as a fundamental expression of human beings' struggle with the absurdity of existence.

VI.5 Implications for Contemporary Ethics

⁶ Hannah Arendt, *The Banality of Evil*, Chapter 6, pp. 252–253 (English edition).

⁷ Friedrich Nietzsche, *Thus Spoke Zarathustra*, Chapter 6, pp. 345–347 (German edition).

This analysis suggests several important implications for understanding human behavior and ethical decision-making. Firstly, the traditional moral framework of vice as simple weakness fails to capture the complex existential role it plays in human motivation and action. Secondly, vice-driven behavior often serves as a mechanism for coping with existential anxiety, providing illusory meaning in the face of absurdity. Thirdly, the relationship between individual agency and vice-driven action requires a more nuanced understanding than conventional moral philosophy typically provides. In any sufficiently complex formal system that maintains logical consistency, Gödel's incompleteness theorems reveal an intrinsic epistemological paradox: the inevitable existence of propositions that defy internal proof. This profound mathematical insight exposes a fundamental tension at the core of rational thought—a system's coherence demands the acceptance of true yet unprovable statements, thereby challenging the very foundations of logical reasoning. Gödel's groundbreaking theorems definitively demonstrate the impossibility of constructing a complete and self-contained knowledge system. When a system purports to prove every proposition within its domain, it necessarily introduces internal contradictions—an inherent limitation that reason cannot transcend. This paradoxical constraint unveils the profound absurdity embedded within rational frameworks, revealing that the quest for absolute logical comprehension is fundamentally futile. Contrary to the conventional understanding that reason exists to resolve ambiguity, it is, in fact, structurally defined by its own inherent absurdity. Humans do not merely inhabit an absurd world; through rational inquiry, we actively generate and perpetuate a form of intellectual paradox. By constructing knowledge systems that invariably confront their own epistemological boundaries, we enact a continuous dialectic between logical aspiration and fundamental limitation. The absurdity of reason, therefore, is not a mere consequence of existential meaninglessness, but an essential, generative feature of the rational process itself which further lead to the existence of vice playing a role of self-motivation. The examination of vice-driven behavior through an existentialist lens reveals a profound paradox at the heart of human experience. While individuals possess the capacity for rational choice and moral action, they remain vulnerable to the seductive pull of vice—not merely as a moral failing, but as an expression of deeper existential struggles. This understanding suggests that addressing vice-driven behavior requires more than moral education or institutional controls; it demands a recognition of the fundamental existential conditions that make such behavior both compelling and destructive. The persistence of vice-driven action, despite its self-destructive nature, points to what might be termed an "existential trap"—a situation where the very mechanisms humans employ to cope with existence's meaninglessness become sources of further alienation and suffering. This dynamic helps explain why even the most noble individuals cannot entirely escape the contradictions and tensions inherent in human existence, and why societies continue to repeat patterns of self-destructive behavior despite historical lessons.

VII Discussion & Conclusion

Exploring vice as a form of self-driven motivation through the lens of existentialism and absurdism offers profound insights into the complexities of human nature. Existentialism, with its emphasis on individualism and the inherent freedom and responsibility of human existence, reveals how vice often emerges from our relentless search for meaning in a universe that offers no intrinsic purpose. Thinkers like Heidegger, Sartre, and Camus illustrate how individuals, faced with feelings of alienation and existential dread, may resort to vices to cope with the absurdity of existence. These vices become not merely moral failings but powerful responses to our fundamental uncertainty. Sartre's concept of bad faith exemplifies this dynamic, showing how individuals evade their true freedom by conforming to societal norms or engaging in self-deception. Such actions obscure the authentic self and reflect the struggle to reconcile personal desires with external expectations. In contrast, absurdism, particularly as articulated by Camus, frames vice as a natural reaction to the irrationality of the universe. In a world where traditional values and moral structures appear irrelevant,

individuals often turn to vice to assert their existence and create personal meaning in a chaotic and indifferent cosmos. The absurdist hero, exemplified by Camus's depiction of Sisyphus, embodies this struggle. Despite the recognition of life's futility, the absurdist hero resists despair by embracing their freedom to choose, using vice as a means of metaphysical defiance—choosing meaning even in the face of ultimate meaninglessness. This dynamic between existential freedom, vice, and meaning is vividly illustrated in both literary and historical case studies. Characters like Meursault in Camus's *The Stranger* and figures in Molière's *The Imaginary Invalid* show how vice becomes a vehicle for personal rebellion, a way of confronting the absurdity of life and asserting one's identity in a universe that offers no clear answers. These figures illustrate that vice is not simply the breakdown of moral integrity but the existential response to life's inherent contradictions. Through their vices, they attempt to forge meaning, assert their agency, and reclaim their autonomy in the face of an indifferent universe.

In conclusion, this exploration reveals the multifaceted role of vice in human motivation. Through the lenses of existentialism and absurdism, vice is shown not as a mere moral failing but as a manifestation of our struggle to assert identity and meaning in a universe that resists both. It highlights the tension between freedom and responsibility, where individuals, though free to choose, must confront the existential consequences of their actions. By embracing their vices, individuals do not necessarily escape moral judgment, but rather navigate the complexities of existence with a sense of agency and resilience. Moreover, this understanding challenges us to reconsider our own choices and values in a world that may not offer intrinsic meaning. As Sartre and Camus suggest, the recognition of life's absurdity can lead not to nihilism, but to a form of existential rebellion—the active engagement with the world despite its inherent meaninglessness. Future research should delve deeper into the psychological and social dimensions of vice, further investigating its role in the human search for meaning. As we confront the existential challenges of our own time, including the anxieties of modernity and the search for self-identity in a hyper-connected, post-truth world, understanding vice as an existential tool can offer profound insights into how we navigate the complexities of contemporary life. Ultimately, by acknowledging the existential function of vice, we can better understand how individuals negotiate life's contradictions. Rather than viewing vice solely as a moral or psychological flaw, we can see it as a form of personal exploration—a rebellion against the absurd, a creative act that affirms existence in a world that offers no answers. In this way, vice can be viewed as a vehicle for self-creation, enabling individuals to face the uncertainties of existence and assert their own meaning in a world that resists easy explanations.

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